

Analysis of sodium diuranate for organic flocculent content

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Abstract : Sodium diuranate (SDU) produced through hydrometallurgical process such as carbonate leaching process from uranium ores containing high levels of carbonate contains significant levels of organic flocculent. When such a SDU was used as a raw material for the production of nuclear fuel, the flocculent appears in the uranyl nitrate pure solution in a spongy form and makes it hazy. Thus, it becomes mandatory to initially ascertain for content of flocculent in SDU and to look for a means to remove the same completely before processing. This paper describes a method to determine the content of organic flocculent in SDU. The chemical procedure involves complete removal of carbonate present in sodium diuranate by reacting it with phosphoric acid, followed by the determination of the carbon content in the dried residue using a carbon-sulphur analyzer and later correlating the content of the organic flocculent in terms of organic carbon content. The deduction is based on the calibration curve obtained experimentally by carrying out the same methodology using known quantities of organic flocculent both in the absence and presence of SDU (Correlation coefficients (R^2) respectively are 0.9998 and 0.9994). By the present method the content of carbon in the organic flocculent determined experimentally both in absence as well as in presence of matrix were found to be 28.97% and 28.48%, respectively, and content of organic flocculent in the SDU was determined to be 1.5%. The moisture content in the organic flocculent was also determined and based on this value it is concluded that SDU contains 1.2% virgin organic flocculent.

Keywords : Carbonate leaching process, uranyl tricarbano complex, sodium diuranate, organic flocculent, solvent extraction, hazy uranyl nitrate pure solution.

Introduction

Carbonate leaching process is one of the hydrometallurgical processes widely used^{1,2} for recovering uranium from ores especially containing high levels of carbonate content as is a very convenient process for its adaptation on large scale. The carbonate leaching process involve intimate contacting of the uranium bearing ore with the solution of sodium carbonate and sodium bicarbonate mixture solution thereby bringing uranium present in the ore into solution in the form of a soluble uranyl tricarbano complex $[\text{UO}_2(\text{CO}_3)_3]^{4-}$ followed by separation of undissolved material by filtration to obtain a clear pregnant leach solution. Uranium present in the soluble state in the form of $[\text{UO}_2(\text{CO}_3)_3]^{4-}$ is precipitated with sodium hydroxide and this sodium diuranate slurry is thickened and is filtered to obtain sodium diuranate cake. Handling of low-grades of uranium results in very dilute clear pregnant leach solution and subsequent process also contains an amount of the leach solution. This necessitates thickening of the precipitate containing leach solution and there-

fore, the it is necessary to add flocculent as settling aid.

When the SDU obtained by extracting uranium from uranium ores with the carbonate leaching process is used as a raw material for the production of nuclear fuel, the presence of flocculent in the SDU hampers the counter current solvent extraction process of uranyl nitrate slurry with the organic extractant tri-*n*-butyl phosphate in kerosene. The resulting uranyl nitrate pure solution (UNPS) thus obtained is hazy and observed to contain some foreign material in a spongy form which is attributed to the presence of organic flocculent by its physical characteristics. Thus, use of uranyl nitrate feed obtained by the digestion of the SDU containing the organic flocculent not only affect the performance of solvent extraction and stripping processes but also the quality of the uranyl nitrate pure solution, raffinate and lean solvent. Impairing the quality of process streams has a recurring impact on the overall purification process as the solvent is being reused and the entire process lines are likely to be loaded with the undesirable solid material generated due to the

presence of flocculent in the process streams. Processing of such uranyl nitrate pure solution to obtain uranium oxide powder may result in poor sinterability of the pellets which are further encapsulated in a zircaloy cladding tube to be used in the nuclear power reactors. Thus, it is essential to know the presence or absence of flocculant in the SDU before proceeding with the SDU as a raw material for nuclear fuel production.

Determination of organic flocculant such as polyacrylamide in aqueous solutions has been studied extensively³⁻⁸. However, all these methods are based on determination of dissolved flocculant in water where there are little or no interferences. Whereas determination of presence of flocculant in the SDU by any solution technique necessitates dissolution of the sample in acid thereby ensuring complete dissolution of the flocculant besides avoiding the major interference from metal ions especially that from uranium. The present methodology described here does not require dissolution of the sample and presence of uranium does not contribute to any serious interference.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of analytical reagent grade. The determination of content of total carbon as well as organic carbon was done with carbon and sulphur analyzer CS 600, LECO Make, USA. For determining organic carbon the sample was treated with dilute phosphoric acid.

Procedure : To the sodium diuranate sample of about 100 mg accurately weighed in a ceramic crucible (using a balance of accuracy ± 0.0001 g) 50% phosphoric acid was added through a weight burette in a drop by drop manner till all the carbonate reacts completely. The crucible was then placed in an air oven at 100 °C for about ten hours. The carbon content in the residue in the ceramic crucible was determined using the carbon and sulphur analyzer.

Two sets of ceramic crucibles, four in each set, were used for the experiments. In one set of ceramic crucibles only organic flocculant of varying quantities was taken and in another set varying amounts of SDU sample as well as varying amounts of organic flocculant were taken. All the samples in the crucibles were treated with phosphoric acid as described in the procedure and the organic carbon content in the dried residues were determined using carbon and sulphur analyzer.

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Results and discussion

Sodium diuranate contains considerable quantities of carbonate and it is known that presence of $p\%$ carbonate in the SDU contributes to about $0.2p\%$ of carbon in the material. Thus, deduction of content of organic flocculant present in the SDU based on the total carbon content in SDU is erroneous. It is essential to eliminate the carbonate present in the SDU completely before determining the content of carbon in the residue. Complete removal of carbonate from SDU is accomplished by addition of phosphoric acid. Though it is possible to remove carbonate with any mineral acid such as nitric, sulphuric or hydrochloric acid, it is desirable to use only phosphoric acid for the reasons mentioned here. Removal of carbonate by the addition of mineral acids obviously lead to the formation of metal sulphates, metal nitrates or metal chlorides. As part of determining organic carbon the residue is subjected to heating to elevated temperatures in a ceramic crucible and the temperatures are conducive for the decomposition of metal sulphates, metal nitrates and metal chlorides which on decomposition produce undesirable gases such as SO_x , NO_x , or Cl_2 . For example, typical decomposition of a metal sulphate⁹ can be represented as

where, (s) stands for solid phase.

Similarly, thermal decomposition of metal nitrates also is reported¹⁰. Though the procedure involves use of suitable chemical traps for avoiding the interference from the undesirable gases that emanate during the heating of the sample in the C&S analyzer's furnace to elevated temperatures, it is preferable to minimize the possible sources of generation of undesirable gases. When the first drop of dilute phosphoric acid is added to the sample in a ceramic crucible phenomenon of frothing can be visually observed depending on the content of carbonate present in the sample. Proper location of phosphoric acid drop falling into the sample as well as adequate time for complete reaction of the added drop of the acid must be ensured to maintain the excess acid remaining at a minimum level even after complete removal of carbonate.

Similarly, wetting of the entire sample in the ceramic crucible must also be ensured to avoid presence of unreacted carbonate after completion of the phosphoric acid addition to derive reliable results of analysis. The graphs plotted for quantity of flocculant against the quantity of carbon experimentally obtained in two cases :

In the absence of sodium diuranate is

$$y = 0.2897x + 0.0001; R^2 = 0.9998; \text{ and}$$

in the presence of sodium diuranate is

$$y = 0.2848x + 0.0002; R^2 = 0.9994 \text{ are linear}$$

where y = quantity of carbon (in g) obtained by experiment and x = quantity of organic flocculant (in g) taken in the ceramic crucible. The graphs are shown in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively.

From these two linear plots it is clear by the present method that the content of carbon in the organic flocculant

Fig. 1. Carbon content in flocculant as determined in the absence of SDU.

Fig. 2. Carbon content in flocculant as determined in the presence of SDU.

determined experimentally both in the absence of matrix and presence of matrix to be 28.97% and 28.48%, respectively, indicating the close agreement between the carbon content values determined without and with the presence of sodium diuranate matrix. Organic flocculant used for flocculating aqueous particle suspensions normally belongs to the family of polyacrylamides. It is a nonionic polymer and to increase its reactivity it's modified form such as the anionic form is used. Normally, the anionic form of polyacrylamide is obtained by the hydrolysis of polyacrylamide¹¹ in alkaline solutions which can be represented as following :

Molecular weight of sodium polyacrylamide (M) can be expressed in terms of number of monomer units of acrylamide (n) and number of hydrolyzed monomer units of acrylamide (m) as

$$71n + 23m + 2$$

From this, it is possible to calculate the %carbon in the flocculant as

$$\frac{3600n}{71n + 23m + 2} \text{ and}$$

$$\%N \text{ content as } \frac{1400(n - m)}{71n + 23m + 2}$$

From these expressions, it can be calculated that in an acrylamide monomer, $n = 1$ and $m = 0$, the %carbon and %N are respectively 49.32 and 19.18%. However, in the normally used polyacrylamide anionic polymers, the nitrogen content is specified as below 0.1% indicating that the polyacrylamide is more than 99.5% hydrolyzed

$$\text{i.e. } m = 0.995n.$$

In polyacrylamide (of anionic type) containing nitrogen content of about 0.1%, the carbon content should be of the order 38%. Polyacrylamide has great affinity towards water and it absorbs water on storage depending on the ambient conditions of its storage. The carbon content determined thus is that present in the flocculant as in the state in which it is stored. Thus, to know the carbon

content in the virgin flocculant, it is required to know the content of moisture in the flocculant. However, storage conditions of a flocculant used on a bulk scale are conducive to absorb moisture and thus the content of carbon in the as stored flocculant may vary from lot to lot of the flocculant. The content of moisture in the flocculant is determined gravimetrically to be 19.7%.

The organic carbon content in SDU experimentally obtained by following the present method is 0.436%. The carbon content in the as stored flocculant is 28.725%. Thus, the content of flocculant in the SDU can simply be deduced as 1.5%. However, if it is preferred to deduce the content of flocculant present in SDU in the form of virgin flocculant, it can be deduced to be 1.2% based on the moisture content in the flocculant.

Conclusion

The present method described above is useful to reasonably estimate the content of an organic flocculant present in an intermediate product like sodium diuranate and the method is easy, reliable and convenient to be adopted as a routine analytical tool for day to day analysis.

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